

EUTR implementation in the Italian wood-energy sector: role and impact of (ongoing) digitalisation

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1. Introduction

Widespread illegal logging and wood trading have resulted in rapid and catastrophic deterioration of the environment (Trishkin et al., 2015). In particular, illegal logging has been regarded as a chronic problem throughout the world, and this fact has spurred major international efforts to control its associated trade (Maryudi et al., 2020). Moreover, illegal logging is seen as one of the key drivers of deforestation and forest degradation, and it accounts for up to 10-30% of global logging (FAO/UNEP, 2020; Leipold, 2017). Illegal activities usually include a wide array of practices: incorrect estimations of wood volume and quality, overestimating the age of trees (permitting an earlier harvest), altering the stand density to apply clearcutting, initiating paid afforestation which never materialises, or performing salvage cuttings applied to healthy and vigorous trees as well as illegal harvesting and illegal transport and export of logs (Gavrilit et al., 2016). Illegally sourced timber is estimated to cost, on average, 16% less than legal wood, ~~so that it creates unfair competition for legally operating businesses, as since~~ illegal operators sidestep duties and taxes, ~~contributing to unfair competition and significant losses of government revenues and they have no obligation to invest in proper management of forests losses as well~~ (Maryudi et al., 2020). Thus, illegal logging not only impacts some of the world's most vulnerable and threatened forests but also affects state revenue, global market prices for timber and wood products, and local livelihood (Moser and Leipold, 2021).

The EU is one of the world's largest timber importers, even if there is a considerable cross-country variation across Member States. It accounts ~~ed~~ for more than 35% of total world imports of timber and timber products ~~in 2017~~, and between 2012 and 2017 ~~the~~ imports from non-EU countries registered a cumulative annual growth rate of 5% ~~-%~~ (Moral-Pajares et al., 2020; [United Nations International Trade Statistics Database, 2017](#)). Although almost three-quarters of these trade flows are within the EU, part of this trade between EU members is in timber or timber products initially purchased from outside the EU (Moral-Pajares et al., 2020). As far as wood-energy is concerned, it is currently the most important renewable energy source for heating, but a large part of this wood is sourced from uncertified forests (Sikkema et al., 2017).

Public and private concerns about the impacts of illegal logging were addressed at the EU level by adopting the European Timber Regulation [n.995/2010](#) (EUTR) in 2010 (Sotirov et al., 2017). It has been part of a suite of initiatives to promote sustainable forestry by removing illegal timber from global supply chains (McDermott and Sotirov, 2018). The EUTR approach, in particular, has been expected to yield substantial environmental and social stewardship in the forest sector (Moser and Leipold, 2021). However, matching both environmental and socio-economic objectives, the EUTR has lacked one coherent policy goal, with implementation problems as a consequence (Leipold et al., 2016). Each Member State is responsible for determining how to control the legality of its imports and how sanctions are applied if necessary (Ituarte-Lima et al., 2019; Moser and Leipold, 2021). In some ~~European countries~~ [EU member states](#), the formal implementation of the EUTR has proven to be a slower process than in others. The EU Commission concluded that implementation and compliance by operators have been uneven across the Member States. Numerous challenges still exist depending on enterprise size, the complexity of traded products and sourcing countries (Acheampong and Maryudi, 2020). Therefore, it is not surprising that the EU Member States have performed relatively low rates of compliance checks among importing operators (Köthke, 2020).

1 According to Eurostat (2021), over the period 2011-2020, Italy, despite imported on average 1.02
2 million cubic meters of fuelwood (including wood for charcoal) and 1.32 million cubic meters of wood
3 chips. Despite being one of the largest worldwide importers of firewood and the fourth largest
4 importer of wood residues, particles and chips, and the first European importer of pellets for
5 residential use (Crivellaro and Ruffinatto, 2020; Secco et al., 2017), these products, Italy has not been
6 particularly proactive in the domestic implementation of the EUTR to establish both penalties and
7 a system of checks to encourage legal behaviour among economic operators effectively (Crivellaro
8 and Ruffinatto, 2020; McDermott and Sotirov, 2018; Secco et al., 2017).

11 As the entire procedure of EUTR enforcement is mainly based on traceability verification following a
12 “paper-based” approach aimed to assess risks and introduce mitigating measures (UNEP-WCMC,
13 2020), operators are encouraged to produce adequate documentation as proof of legally sourced
14 timber (Cashore and Stone, 2012). However, traceability represents an interesting application
15 scenario for digital technologies (Rolandi et al., 2021), since emerging digital solutions could make the
16 massive exchange of data and information more effective and efficient, lowering policy-related
17 transaction and costs associated with EUTR implementation.

21 ~~This policy paper aims to stimulate the debate on the impact of digitalisation in implementing EUTR
22 in the wood-energy sector, a traditionally low tech sector with a limited importance in terms of value-
23 added creation, where administrative burden may hinder the achievement of traceability goals. To
24 this purpose, the paper presents the main findings of participatory activities conducted in a Living Lab
25 composed by 25 stakeholders with different expertise from September 2020 to April 2021, aimed to
26 assess the impact of digitalisation on EUTR implementation and traceability in the Italian wood-energy
27 sector. A Living Lab is defined as a ‘research methodology aimed at co-creating innovation through
28 the involvement of aware users in a real life setting’ (Dietrich et al., 2021). It has received extensive
29 political support as part of regional development policies and, most recently, as a potential tool for
30 analysing and supporting the local transition towards more sustainable agri-food systems (Gamache
31 et al., 2020). In a Living Lab, user needs are central, and collaborative learning is undertaken by users,
32 stakeholders and researchers in a real life environment. In fostering the interaction between science
33 and society, Living Labs are also of scientific value since they provide a unique setting for collective
34 innovation in the context of societal challenges involving heterogeneous stakeholders (such as but not
35 limited to citizens, customers, policy makers, researchers, educators, businesses and universities) to
36 significantly contribute to the development of sustainable public policy (Kalinauskaitė et al., 2021).~~

44 Against this backdrop, this paper aims to assess the impacts of the uptake of digital technologies on
45 the EUTR enforcement and implementation in the wood-energy sector, so as to stimulate a debate
46 between stakeholders and policymakers about possible future interventions in this field. Even if this
47 is a traditionally low tech sector with a limited importance in terms of value-added creation, our
48 research hypothesis is that digitalisation is able to generate both positive and negative impacts on the
49 implementation of the EUTR, respectively fostering or hindering the achievement of traceability goals
50 in the wood-energy sector.

54 The paper is organised as follows. ~~Next~~The next section reviews the implementation of the EUTR at a
55 national level, highlighting issues and opportunities at stake. Then, material and methods are
56 described before the impacts of the application of digital technologies on traceability and EUTR
57 implementation are analysed ~~and discussed~~. Lastly, final policy recommendations are provided.

2. EUTR enforcement at the national level: issues and opportunities

1
2 According to a growing body of literature, EUTR incurs in some degree of bureaucracy and places
3 disproportionate burdens on specific actors along with production networks (Maryudi et al., 2020).
4 Traceability obligations and due diligence requirements for European operators (entailing access to
5 information on imported timber, risk assessment procedures, risk mitigation measures and
6 procedures) are not only tedious but also costly since they imply an extra workload introducing
7 accurate documentation (Brusselaers and Buysse, 2021; Giurca and Jonsson, 2015). It follows that
8 implementing timber traceability, due diligence systems, and corresponding sanctions certainly
9 requires appropriate capacity and resources in terms of finances, personnel, expertise and technical
10 equipment, both for target groups (operators, traders) and for Competent Authorities (Gavriliuț et al.,
11 2016).

12
13 ~~Operators and stakeholders~~ Stakeholders (including also operators) have expressed concern and
14 complained about the complicated documentation requirements and the burdensome nature of the
15 EUTR due diligence process that has increased the cost of trading timber (Giurca et al., 2013; Masiero
16 et al., 2015). The number of required documents included certificate of business registration, tax
17 identification number, tax clearance certificate, social security and national insurance trust clearance
18 certificate, timber utilisation contract, proof of payment of forest levies, tree information form, log
19 information form, export contract, export permit, log measurement and conveyance certificate,
20 phytosanitary certificate, among others (Acheampong and Maryudi, 2020; Sikkema et al., 2017). Some
21 authors argued that such a “paper-based” approach is not expensive but manually intensive, leading
22 to errors and delays (Appelhanz et al., 2016). Due to technical, organisational, and financial barriers,
23 some smallholders and industries struggle to engage in legality verification. In contrast, large
24 industries and exporters accumulate more benefits due to their scale and pre-existing capacity
25 (Maryudi et al., 2020).

26
27 Since the volume of information and documentation rises as much as the distance between
28 production and consumption increases, attention is increasingly focused on digital technologies to
29 enhance transparency in the global supply chains (Ebinger and Omondi, 2020; Ehlers et al., 2021).
30 Since each Member State is responsible for determining how to control timber legality (McDermott
31 and Sotirov, 2018), in countries dominated by a strongly differentiated administrative landscape,
32 Governments and public administrations might take advantage of digital and innovative solutions to
33 improve policies enforcement (Carstens, 2021). As a whole, the application of digital solutions for
34 traceability of forest resources, from origin to end-use, may offer enormous potential to support the
35 sector and further contribute to global sustainability, enhancing European value chains, and fighting
36 corrupt practices associated with illegal imports (Brunori et al., 2021). Digital solutions, in fact, include
37 computer-based information systems for recognition, traceability, log tracking and monitoring,
38 including barcodes, Quick Response (QR) codes, microchips, fingerprints, isotopes, Radio Frequency
39 Identification (RFID) transponders and blockchain (Corona et al., 2017; Tzoulis et al., 2014). For
40 instance, a QR code can be marked in a tree log by lasers and then it can be read using a smart phone
41 application, whereas very durable RFID tags can be planted inside a wood log and transmit data to
42 receivers contributing to traceability (Sperandio et al., 2017).

43
44 However, these innovative and digital log-tracking solutions are not particularly practical and tend to
45 be high cost, also because sometimes they require high-level specialists and then are difficult to apply

on a large scale, if not for large companies able to process high volumes of biomass for energy purposes (Schraml et al., 2020; Watkinson et al., 2020).

The relevant research question for policymakers and stakeholders is then the following: how to activate a pathway for digitalisation of the forestry sector that can address the problems of illegal logging in different contexts? Our case study, based on the results of the work of a Living Lab (LL) in Italy constituted within the H2020 project DESIRA, addresses is aimed to offer an answer to this question and demand.

3. Traceability and EUTR implementation in the Italian wood-energy sector: ~~context and~~ assessing the impacts of digitalisation

3.1 Materials and methods

The paper develops an inclusive approach to formulating agenda-setting digitalisation on EUTR implementation and traceability in the Italian wood-energy sector. The participatory approach was based on Living Lab activities, which took place from September 2020 to April 2021. A Living Lab is defined as a 'research methodology aimed at co-creating innovation through the involvement of aware users in a real-life setting' (Dietrich et al., 2021). It has received extensive recognition in academic and political areas as a potential tool for analysing and supporting the local transition towards more sustainable agri-food and forestry systems (Arnould et al., 2022; Gamache et al., 2020). In a Living Lab, user-needs are central, and collaborative learning is undertaken by users, stakeholders and researchers in a real-life environment. In fostering the interaction between science and society, Living Labs are also of scientific value since they provide a unique setting for collective innovation in the context of societal challenges involving heterogeneous stakeholders (such as but not limited to citizens, customers, policy-makers, researchers, educators, businesses and universities) to significantly contribute to the development of sustainable public policy (Kalinauskaite et al., 2021).

In more detail, the Living Lab mobilised knowledge from 25 stakeholders, which were preliminarily identified from a mapping activity and then formally invited. This exercise allowed to cover main categories of stakeholders, as follows: forest owners, operators and their associations (4 participants), public administrations (2), non-government organizations (4), private industrial companies (4), universities (2) and research centres (2), practitioners and consultants (5), certification and control body (1), and journalists (1). After a preliminary desk analysis aimed to review both scientific and grey literature on the topic under investigation, two online workshops were organised in October and December 2020 (participation rates were, respectively, 92% and 80%) aimed to assess needs, expectations and impacts related to the uptake of digital technologies in the wood-energy sector. The first workshop was organised in two sessions. After an introductory speech, stakeholders were first asked to analyze the context under analysis, elaborating a SWOT analysis and identifying the main needs related to the uptake of digital technologies to achieve traceability goals. Afterwards, they participated in identifying main (social, physical and digital) entities, activities and relationships at stake in the wood-energy sector. The second workshop was also split into three sessions. First, a follow-up session allowed stakeholders to validate the results of the first workshops. Then, after a short introduction, participants were asked to identify main digital technologies at stake in the wood-energy sector for traceability purposes. Lastly, based on a template containing a list of items and structured questions elaborated and provided by the DESIRA project research team (see Annex), participatory activities revolved around identifying and evaluating impacts of the digitalisation process

1 on traceability and EUTR implementation in the wood-energy sector. Likewise, determinants of these
2 impacts were identified and assessed.

3
4 As a rule of thumb, after an introductory presentation of the topic, participation in each session was
5 stimulated by a group of moderators. Therefore, stakeholders were continuously asked to intervene
6 in chat and take part in an open debate. Moreover, online participatory tools such as interactive
7 boards and online surveys were largely used, both in plenary and working group sessions. The latter
8 were organised and managed using specific digital breakout rooms with at least one moderator for
9 the group, in order to allow a higher level of analysis of specific topics.

12 **3.12 Context analysis**

14 According to the National Forest and Carbon Sink Inventory (CREA and Carabinieri Forestali, 2015),
15 there are 10.9 million hectares of forest in Italy, which is 37% of the national land area. Italian forest
16 area has constantly increased in the last decades (+4.9% in the decade 2005-2015), mainly because of
17 the abandonment of agricultural activities in the mountain and hilly areas- (Agnoletti et al., 2022;
18 Pallotta et al., 2022). However, due to several reasons (mainly depopulation and ageing in mountain
19 and remote areas, ISTAT 2020a), the Italian forestry sector has been largely affected by a continuous
20 decrease in forestry activities. Consequently, only ~~a small percentage~~18% of Italian forests is actively
21 managed by means of forestry plans, and only 852,000 forest hectares (~~ISTAT, 2020b~~) are certified
22 according to existing certification schemes- (Corona and Gismondi, 2019; ISTAT, 2020b).

24 Thus, even if wood biomass for energy purposes (i.e. firewood, pellet and woodchips) represents the
25 first renewable energy source for heating in Italy (Pra and Pettenella, 2016), it mainly comes from
26 abroad. According to the United Nations International Trade Statistics Database (2017), Italy in 2015
27 was the first world importer of firewood, the fourth importer of pellet and among the first ten
28 importers of woodchips. ~~Some structural characteristics of the Italian wood energy market (such as~~
29 ~~the prevalence of an informal economy based on unrecorded and unregulated transactions, a~~
30 ~~wide presence of micro and small enterprises operating in local value chains, and the relevant role of self-~~
31 ~~consumption), all contributes to the lack of traceability of imported wood biomass for energy purposes~~
32 ~~and to the prevalence of informal economic activities in forestry areas~~ (Pra and Pettenella, 2016). In
33 the case of firewood, it is estimated that 14 out of 20 million tons consumed annually are not
34 registered (and therefore tracked) at all (Legambiente, 2016). Notwithstanding, the low priority given
35 to the EUTR in the national political agenda, the complexity of the legislative system, a highly
36 fragmented and decentralised institutional framework, and the economic crisis have been cited as the
37 main reasons for the delay in the formal domestic implementation of the EUTR in Italy since its entered
38 into force (Secco et al., 2017). Although the national Competent Authority (i.e. the Ministry of
39 ~~Agriculture~~Agricultural, Food and ~~Forestry~~Forestry Policies) has increased the number of checks aimed to fine
40 non-compliant operators (from 21 in 2015 to 577 in the second semester of 2018), there is still a large
41 room for manoeuvre to make this procedure more effective.

42 Moreover, it must be considered that more than 80% of forest areas (representing the 'backbone' of
43 the Italian wood-energy sector) is located in the so-called 'inner areas', which correspond to the 'areas
44 with development issues' according to the EAFRD classification (Storti, 2016). In these areas, where
45 wood and biomass for energy purposes is largely produced, factors like ageing, low digital literacy,
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scarce attitudes to embrace newness and changes, lack of digital infrastructure and connectivity greatly affect the low uptake of digital technologies (Rete Rurale Nazionale, 2017).

3.23 Impacts of digitalisation and its determinants

Implementing digitally-enabled traceability systems requires a relevant set of socio-technical conditions that may enable or limit their uptake. Therefore, a deep understanding of the socio-economic, environmental and technological context is needed to investigate the impacts of these digital solutions in a given application scenario, such as the wood-energy sector. Henceforth, we report the main evidences that emerged from participatory activities conducted during our Living Lab.

In the workshops organised within the Living Lab, stakeholders recognised that two technologies could be considered key enablers of digitalisation: digital payments (e.g. e-invoicing, point of sales) and digital platforms. As for digital payments, Appelhanz et al. (2016) observed that electronic traceability of transactions enables automatic data import, simple data accumulation, and information provision to internal and external data processing. About digital forest innovation platforms (as called by Pynnönen et al., 2021), they provide operational tools for forest data sharing, decision-support, e-government operations, and connecting forest owners and service providers. Ebinger and Omondi (2020, p.8) recognised that *'the commonality among emerging digital approaches in supply chains management is a trend towards 'datafication' that is increasingly leading to the translation of the physical world into data, which could then be used to support decision-making in a dynamic, problem-oriented, and tailor-made way by combining data from various supply chain actors'*. For example, such a 'datification' could help companies and Competent Authorities to reliably record, check and measure traceability performances to strengthen the implementation of the EUTR. Examples are the Intrastat portal of the Customs and Monopolies Agency, where data and information related to import and/or sale of biomass for energy purposes are stored in digital format within digital portals, as well as the implementation of an upcoming public data warehouse implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry Policies to manage the enforcement of the EUTR regulation. Another interesting example is the Monitoring Organisation "Conlegno" portal, named "LegnOKweb", a tool that allows to perform the Due Diligence System in three steps (Access to Information, Risk Analysis, any Risk Mitigation).

Such According to the Living Lab, such a switch from hard copy to digital solutions aimed to foster information exchange between competent authorities and forestry companies and speed up the enforcement of verification and inspection activities related to the EUTR is ongoing. The Living Lab recognised that the uptake of digital payments and invoices, on the one hand, and digital platforms and portals, on the other hand, impacts on traceability and EUTR enforcement, since they both affect activities and relationships in the wood-energy sector (table 1). As a result of this participatory activity, table 1 was elaborated to capture and describe the main positive and negative impacts of each technology under analysis.

Table 1: Main impacts of digitalisation on EUTR implementation in the wood-energy sector in Italy

Digital technology	Positive impact	Negative impact

<p>Payments for wood for energy have been increasingly digitalised. The main technologies involved in digital payments are a point of sale (POS) and e-invoicing. However, even if growing, the process is still minimal.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforced traceability of payments • Deployed safer and simpler solutions for payments • Enhanced transparency in business relationships • Increased responsibility of the woman in managing administrative and management tasks within family companies • Lessened opportunities for tax avoidance/evasion • Increased availability of reliable data on wood-energy production • Limited socio-economic dumping (unfair price competition) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased costs for SMEs (e-invoicing services, devices) • Arisen difficulty for SMEs to address the increasing need for digital skills (for instance: to hire/to train skilled employees for managing software and similar). • Marginalised forest companies in areas with low broadband coverage • Increased technical and practical difficulties in using tools and software for digital payments.
<p>Authorisation of cut wood and administrative controls related to the EUTR enforcement rely on information and data that are being (slowly) digitised. Such an ongoing process relies on online portals and digital platforms.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerated communications between EUTR managing authorities, public administrations and forest companies involved in the production of biomass for energy use • Speeded up documentary checks related to compliance with EUTR • Increased availability of data for policy planning, public research, final users • Enhanced transparency in administrative decisions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased administrative and managerial costs for the digital transition of public administrations • Proliferation of web services with different characteristics (not interoperable and not fully reliable) • Induced reluctance to accept, use and manage new digital tools and portals in managing authorities • Arisen risks for data protection (and reluctance to share information)

Source: our elaboration from Living Lab activities

What emerges is that digital solutions, building a structured data infrastructure and converting the most important transactions into digital format, may contribute to speeding up documentary checks and communication ~~between~~ among public administrations, EUTR Competent Authorities and forest companies producing wood biomass for energy use. This fact, in turn, improves the availability and reliability of data on wood biomasses production and sales, accelerates both authorisation and control activities related to the EUTR enforcement. Therefore, in line with Rolandi et al. (2021) and Ebinger

and Omondi (2020), digital technologies mediating processes, tasks and a massive exchange of data and information lead to more efficient traceability and tracking activities in global supply chains.

The other side of the coin related to this digitalisation process ~~is that it may entail~~ entails additional costs for companies and public authorities (due to the need for digital upskilling and reskilling and new managerial and organisational patterns. In line with Appelhanz et al. (2016), this phenomenon brings to further marginalisation of (especially small or medium-sized) forest companies in absence of broadband coverage, connectivity and proper digital skills ~~(as revealed by Appelhanz et al., 2016).~~

All these impacts of digital tools on traceability and EUTR implementation strongly depends on three contribution mechanisms, such as technology design, access to digitalisation and system complexity. ~~Table 2 synthetically reports and describes how~~ The Living Lab was asked to analyze and evaluate these latter are able to ~~mechanisms, so as to describe whether and how they can~~ generate impacts on EUTR implementation in the wood-energy sector. Table 2 highlights the results of this participatory activity.

Table 2: Impact pathways of digitalisation in the Italian wood-energy sector.

Contribution mechanisms	Description
Digital technology design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability among platforms and information and communication technologies (ICT) services for e-invoicing, that affects time losses and administrative burden for forest companies and public administrations • Integration of digital devices with software packages for control and management of forest operations • Standardisation of information required and procedures affecting the use of platforms and ICT services • Adaptability of digital tools and easiness to carry out multiple tasks and transactions (e.g. e-payment, document scanning using photo camera, file sharing via <u>an</u> online messaging platform like WhatsApp, file storing via <u>an</u> online cloud, etc.) • Possibility to use different technological devices (tablet, smartphones, smartwatches) to speed up and facilitate the uptake of technologies for digital payments and administrative tasks • Availability of offline use of digital devices for payments and other administrative tasks in mountain areas
Access to digitalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of new skills and abilities towards the use of digital technologies among forest companies and consumers • Lack of digital skills among civil servants, also due to the reduction of employees' turnover in the Italian public administrations • Presence of entrance costs (subscription, membership, fees) for digital payments solutions and digital services
System complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level and quality of public investments in broadband coverage in mountain areas • COVID 19 lockdown triggered online, and digital payments and social distancing fostered the use of digital tools

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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Conflicts related to the use of digital technologies for traceability purposes• Issues related to property, privacy and personal data. |
|--|---|

Source: our elaboration from Living Lab activities

What emerges is that the impact related to the uptake of digital ~~payments, databases and portals in tools in the~~ wood-energy sector largely depends on ~~whether and~~ how ~~these technologies they~~ are designed in order to ensure: high interoperability, ~~use of among~~ different software, devices and supports, platforms, as well as offline access in the absence of fast broadband coverage, ~~and possible integration with software for forestry control and management~~. Likewise, accessibility greatly matters. On the one hand, entrance costs for digital services affect the affordability for forest companies. On the other hand, the need for specific digital skills influences the uptake ~~to of~~ digital tools among forest entrepreneurs and civil servants responsible for implementing the EUTR at the national level. Furthermore, some other relevant system conditions are able to drive the impacts of digital solutions in the wood-energy sector. For instance, the level of (public and private) investments for enhancing broadband coverage and connectivity in the mountain and remote areas, enabling or disabling the diffusion of digital payments, as well as conflicting uses of digital tools, such as digital payments and digital platforms, for traceability purposes and potential issues in terms of property, privacy and personal data.

Unlike Schroeder et al. (2021), these results somehow contradict the fact that digitally-enabled traceability offers automatic advantages such as efficiency through low cost and ease of use. What emerges is that, in line with Ferrari et al. (2022), socio-economic barriers related to lack of competence (i.e. ICT skills) and training as well as lack of funding could hinder the adoption of digital tools and their impacts on wood-energy traceability. Scarce connectivity and lack of interoperability are also key elements that often negatively affect the digitalisation process and distort its impact in rural and mountain economies (Rijswijk et al., 2021).

All things considered, if supported by holistic attitudes, applications and evaluations, the uptake of digital payments and platforms may help stakeholders of the wood-energy sector to familiarizing with pros and cons related to digital solutions and possibly overcoming issues related to bad design, low accessibility and high system complexity. In this regard, these basic digital applications can represent a first important step along the road towards a creation of a digital ecosystem, that – thanks to a wider access to open data and services of technical assistance, improved digital skills, etc. – is able to support and sustain further digitalisation steps in favour of EUTR implementation and traceability in the wood-energy sector. This fact, in turn, paves the road to future applications of more advanced digital solutions in this sector, still largely neglected and unexplored because of poor digital education, high costs of use and wide diffidence and anxiety related to data privacy and cybersecurity.

4 Conclusions and policy recommendations

The present paper delivered some interesting insights on the role of digital technologies for traceability in the wood-energy sector in Italy. Empirical evidence highlighted that impacts of digital tools on the implementation of the EUTR in Italy are multifaceted and still not able to fully overcome traditional issues at stake, so as to boost traceability in the wood-energy sector.

1 Our analysis contributed in revealing that, in the last years, the actual impact of the incoming
2 digitalisation in this sector has been mainly related to the application of some basic digital tools in
3 public administrations and business activities (such as online portals, databases and e-payment tools),
4 that are involved at different stages in the implementation of the EUTR. As of now, the uptake of more
5 advanced digital applications is still lagging behind in the Italian wood-energy sector, being mainly
6 limited to scattered projects and initiatives related to RFID and blockchain solutions.
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9 Results contribute also to filling and preliminary framing the cognitive gap related to the analysis of
10 possible effects related to the adoption of digital technologies to enforce traceability policies in the
11 wood-energy sector. As a consequence, recommendations for policymakers follow.
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13 First and foremost, the ‘low-tech’ nature of the wood-energy sector shall not prevent the
14 identification of (even basic) digital tools, able to contribute to overcoming endemic sectoral,
15 institutional and administrative weaknesses related to the slow implementation of a policy aimed to
16 foster traceability, in a framework characterised by lack of transparency and presence of illegal
17 activities.
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21 Second, we recognised that any kind of analysis on the state of digitalisation in the wood-energy sector
22 shall carefully take into account the geographical dimension and physical location of forest activities
23 in Italy, so as to properly consider longstanding socio-demographic, environmental and economic
24 issues at stake in these inner and mountain areas. Depopulation, ageing, lack of physical and digital
25 infrastructures are all elements that have certainly affected the deployment of digital technologies
26 and their impacts on the implementation of traceability policies, such as the EUTR, is still far from an
27 end.
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31 Moreover, in presence of such a ‘low-tech’ sector the social element is certainly crucial, since
32 digitalisation is largely expected to change, modify or substitute consolidated relationships in
33 administrative and business activities (for instance, dematerialising, replacing or accelerating certain
34 tasks). In more details, the upcoming deployment of digital solutions aimed to enhance the level of
35 transparency and traceability in the wood-energy sector and facilitate the implementation of the EUTR
36 is expecting not only to generate winners, but also losers and opponents.
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40 As a consequence – and this is another recommendation – any possibility of a positive and inclusive
41 impact of digitalisation in the wood-energy sector strongly depends on a massive diffusion of a digital
42 culture among stakeholders, from forest owners and companies to final consumers passing through
43 public administrations and Competent Authorities.
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47 All that said and considered, we urge policymakers to foster a shift from a traditional technology-
48 driven narrative around the interaction between digitalisation and traceability towards a more olistic
49 approach, so as to carefully analyse and overcome potential issues related to technology design and
50 accessibility, taking also into account the complexity of the application context. To this end, in the
51 medium and short run, open and participatory approaches involving stakeholders may contribute to
52 co-design viable and successful policy measures at national and regional level (such as, open access
53 and interoperable digital platforms and portals). In this time span, rather than sporadic disruptive
54 innovations, these measures shall incentivise a large-scale, incremental and more aware use of (basic)
55 digital technologies for traceability in the wood-energy sector, able to relly match their long-lasting
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1 needs and expectations among producers, civil servants and consumers and overcome their
2 scepticism.

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4 A last reflection concerns the method of the Living Lab we used. The method allows researchers to
5 better understand the system where technology is supposed to be incorporated, the needs of the
6 stakeholders, the potential barriers and constraints to technology diffusion. In early stages of
7 digitalisation, understanding these aspects is key to define clear policy objectives and set or revise
8 policy priorities and tools. From the scientific point of view, Living Labs help researchers to develop
9 conceptual models closer to real contexts, and to identify the key empirical variables to take into
10 consideration when designing (or reforming) policies and assessing their implementations.

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14 However, even if Living Lab technique allowed to provide a participatory assessment taking into
15 account and comparing relevant stakeholders' point of views related to the impact of digital
16 technologies on traceability and EUTR implementation in Italy, this methodology reveals at least two
17 potential weaknesses. First, as some relevant stakeholders could be omitted (or could decide to not
18 participate) their evaluations are missing with negative consequences on impact evaluations.
19 Moreover, techniques for online participatory activities could be less effective than those held in
20 presence in terms of stimulating debate, ideas sharing. In conclusion and looking forward, since the
21 digitalisation process aimed to boost EUTR implementation and traceability in the wood-energy sector
22 is at its early stages, policymakers are expected to periodically ask for (and rely on) updated, thorough
23 and holistic evaluations of impacts also related to the most advanced digital tools, still scarcely
24 diffused. To this aim, they shall consider that inclusive and thematic Living Labs could represent a form
25 of governing digital transitions fostering co-creation of solutions in order to better enforce traceability
26 policies and limit illegal logging, contributing to socio-economic and environmental sustainability
27 goals.
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52

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ANNEX

Template for the evaluation of impacts of digitalisation

<u>What has been digitalised? Which digital technologies are involved?</u>	<u>Impacts (Socio-economic-environmental)</u>	
<u>Impact 1</u>	<u>Direct</u>	<u>Negative impact</u>
		<u>Positive impact</u>
	<u>Indirect</u>	<u>Negative impact</u>
		<u>Positive impact</u>
<u>Impact n</u>	<u>Direct</u>	<u>Negative impact</u>
		<u>Positive impact</u>
	<u>Indirect</u>	<u>Negative impact</u>
		<u>Positive impact</u>

Template for the evaluation of the determinants of the impacts of digitalisation

<u>Impact pathways</u>	<u>How? (Some questions to bear in mind for the facilitation)</u>
<u>Digital technology design</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>Which aspects of the technology are highly relevant for the observed effects?</u>
<u>Access to digitalisation</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>How are the observed effects mitigated or exacerbated by the access (or lack thereof) to digitalisation?</u> <u>How human digital skills, access costs, or private ownership of data network are influencing the observed impacts?</u>
<u>System complexity</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>What kind of contextual factors influence the effects observed in the socio-cyber and physical system?</u> <u>How do external forces play a role in the type of effects observed in your focal?</u>

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

SC - conceptualisation, investigation, methodology, visualisation, data curation, writing - original draft.

FB - conceptualisation, methodology, visualisation, supervision, writing - review & editing

AB - conceptualisation, investigation, funding acquisition, supervision, investigation, writing - review & editing

EM – conceptualisation, investigation, methodology, visualisation, data curation, project administration, writing - review & editing

MM - conceptualisation, methodology, writing - review & editing

GB - conceptualisation, funding acquisition, supervision, writing - review & editing.

AF - conceptualisation, investigation, funding acquisition, supervision, project administration, writing - review & editing.

